

Spatial Flux and the Bound State One Dimensional Dirac Equation with a Scalar Potential

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In a number of previous notes, it has been suggested that nonrelativistic mechanics makes use of a function $W(x,t)$, called the wavefunction, which behaves under transformations $x \rightarrow x+a$, $t \rightarrow t+b$ (a, b infinitesimal) like $\exp(ipx-iEt)$, but with p replaced with $\langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle$ and E with $\langle E \text{ conditional} \rangle$, where $\langle ip \text{ conditional} \rangle = i [\text{Sum over } p \text{ } p f_p(t) \exp(ipx)] / W(x,t) = -i d/dx W(x,t)$. The conditional average may be extended to any function of p . (A similar expression holds for functions of E , but with $\exp(-iEt)$). For the relativistic case, $E^2 = p^2 + m_0^2$ ($c=1$). If one extends the idea of conditional averages, one may obtain the Klein Gordon equation. A question arises as to the role of the conditional average in the one dimensional Dirac equation with a scalar potential. In this note, we suggest the Dirac equation with a scalar potential may follow from ideas based on spatial flux $[-i d/dx W(x,t) / W(x,t)]$. First, one writes $[E^2 - (m+Vp(x))^2]$ as a product of linear terms: $[E+ m+Vp(x)]$ and $[E-m-Vp(x)]$ where $Vp(x)$ is the potential. Each of these is like a different average p . Thus, if $-i d/dx W(x,t) / W(x,t)$ is like a flux equal to average p in the nonrelativistic case, one may suggest two flux functions, namely:

$$-i d/dx V(x) / V(x) = [E-m-Vp(x)] \quad \text{and} \quad -i d/dx U(x) / U(x) = [E+ m+V(x)]$$

Here E is a constant for bound states. Both of these expressions have nonrelativistic limits, i.e. $E-m-Vp(x) = E_{\text{nonrel}} - Vp(x)$ and $E+m+Vp(x) = 2m$. Considering the first, one has:

$E_{\text{nonrel}} - Vp(x) = -i d/dx V(x) / V(x)$, but one wants $d/dx d/dx W(x) / W(x)$ for a kinetic type energy. One could set $d/dx V = d/dx W$, but this leaves the problem of the denominator. One may see that the $2m$ in the kinetic energy may come from $E+m+Vp(x)$. Thus, the flux equations as they stand do not seem suitable.

A possible remedy is to insert functions $a(x)$ and $a^{-1}(x)$ in the following manner:

$$-i d/dx V(x) / V(x) = a(x) [E-m-Vp(x)] \quad \text{and} \quad -i d/dx U(x) / U(x) = a^{-1}(x)[E+ m+V(x)] \quad ((1))$$

One may then attempt to solve for $U(x)$ and $V(x)$ and obtain the one dimensional Dirac equation with a scalar potential $Vp(x)$. That is the objective of this note.

Importance of Spatial Flux

The Schrodinger equation does not contain an explicit spatial flux term $-i d/dx W(x,t) / W(x,t)$ and so one may be tempted to ignore it as unimportant. Multiplying this flux by $W^*(x,t)$ and integrating yields zero for a bound state and so one may feel it is of no importance. For the

nonrelativistic case, however, the physical observable, spatial density $W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$, changes in space as spatial flux i.e.

$$d/dx [W W] = \text{bound state density} = 2 W W [dW/d / W] \quad ((2))$$

Furthermore, taking the spatial derivative of the bound state Schrodinger equation yields:

$$-1/2m d/dx^3 W(x) / W(x) + 1/m [d/dx d/dx W(x) / W(x)] [d/dx W(x) / W(x)] = -d/dx Vp(x) \quad ((3))$$

We suggest the spatial flux in this equation is physical and important. In fact, we suggest quantum mechanics is largely based on spatial and time flux. Equation ((3)) which uses flux is important because it seems to relate to the Dirac case of relativistic quantum mechanics. If one examines the linearized equations ((1)) one sees that taking the derivative will yield $-d/dx Vp(x)$ and $d/dx Vp(x)$. In the nonrelativistic case, both of these should be related to ((3)) and spatial flux.

In addition, time flux is $i d/dx W(x,t) / W(x,t)$ which appears in the Schrodinger equation. If it is important, one may also, it seems, suggest that its spatial counterpart should be.

Bound State One Dimensional Dirac Equation

Starting with the idea that spatial flux is important and that $-i d/dx W(x,t) / W(x,t) = \langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle$, one may examine the relativistic expression $E^*E = p^*p + m_0^*m_0$. With a scalar potential (Klein Gordon theory) this becomes: $E^*E = p^*p + (m_0 + Vp(x))^2$ ((4)) where $c=1$. One may write $E^*E - (m_0 + Vp(x))^2$ as two factors $E+m_0+Vp(x)$ and $E-m_0-Vp(x)$. Each of these is proportional to a different average momentum value. Thus, one may consider two functions $U(x)$ and $V(x)$ which change in space as:

$$-i d/dx V(x) / V(x) = [E-m-Vp(x)] \quad \text{and} \quad -i d/dx U(x) / U(x) = [E+m+Vp(x)]$$

One may keep in mind that even though flux is used here, ((4)) contains p^*p which is really an average of $\langle p^*p \rangle$ or $-d/dx d/dx W(x,t) / W(x,t)$.

In the nonrelativistic limit, $E+m+Vp(x) = 2m$ leading to $-id/dx U(x) / U(x) = 2m$ or $U(x) = \exp(-i2mx)$ and

$E-m-Vp(x) = E_{\text{nonrel}} - Vp(x) = -i d/dx V(x) / V(x)$ which should become the time-independent Schrodinger equation. In such a case, one should have a $d/dx d/dx W(x)$ function and not a linear one. Thus, there seem to be problems. One could set $V(x) = d/dx q(x)$, but this still leaves problems with the denominator.

An alternative is to insert a function $a(x)$ and $a^{-1}(x)$ into the equations to obtain:

$$-i \frac{d}{dx} V(x) / V(x) = a(x) [E - m - V_p(x)] \quad \text{and} \quad -i \frac{d}{dx} U(x) / U(x) = a^{-1}(x) [E + m + V(x)] \quad ((1)) \text{ or } ((5))$$

When multiplying, the two equations together, $a(x)$ and its inverse cancel, thus one still linearizes the problem so to speak. Now, however, the average momenta are $a(x) [E - m - V_p(x)]$ and $a^{-1}(x) [E + m + V(x)]$ which is a little strange. The goal is to determine a value for $a(x)$. Examining the force equation may perhaps yield some ideas. Alternatively, one may take the nonrelativistic limit:

$$E - m - V_p(x) = (E_{\text{nonrel}} - V_p(x)) V(x) = [-i \frac{d}{dx} V(x) / V(x)] a(x) \quad \text{and} \quad ((6))$$

$$E + m + V_p(x) = 2m = -i \frac{d}{dx} U(x) / U(x) a^{-1}(x)$$

As argued, the RHS of the first equation of ((6)) should appear as $d/dx d/dx W(x) / W(x)$ to represent kinetic energy. Thus, one may propose that $V(x) = d/dx q(x)$, but this would imply that $a(x) = q(x) / V(x)$. In such a case, $a^{-1}(x) = V(x) / q(x)$ and $2m = -i \frac{d}{dx} U(x) / d/dx q(x)$. This would suggest that $U(x) = q(x)$. Note, by bringing in this mixing, the $2m$ factor from $E + m + V_p(x)$ automatically comes into the denominator of the $d/dx d/dx U(x)$ term creating the nonrelativistic kinetic energy term.

Thus, one suggestion is to use $a(x) = V(x) / U(x)$. This leads to two equations:

$$-i \frac{d}{dx} V(x) / U(x) = [E - m - V_p(x)] \quad \text{and} \quad -i \frac{d}{dx} U(x) / V(x) = [E + m + V_p(x)] \quad ((7))$$

These are, however, the form of the one dimensional bound state Dirac equations for a scalar potential $V_p(x)$ as presented in (1). One may note that no use of Pauli matrices is made here, although one may see that the two equations may be written as one using such matrices.

Comparison with the Klein-Gordon Equation

It may be noted that the without a scalar potential, the Dirac and Klein-Gordon equations are completely consistent. Adding a scalar potential, however, changes matters. For the Klein-Gordon case with a scalar potential, one has:

$$E^* E W(x) = -d/dx d/dx W(x) + (m_0 + V_p(x))^2 W(x) \quad ((8))$$

Here there is one wavefunction $W(x)$. In the nonrelativistic case, $W(x)$ becomes the nonrelativistic wavefunction $W(x)$.

In the Dirac one dimensional case, one has two functions $U(x)$ and $V(x)$. In the nonrelativistic limit, $U(x)$ becomes the nonrelativistic wavefunction $W(x)$, but in the relativistic case $U(x)$ is not the relativistic $W(x)$ of the Klein Gordon equation namely one may obtain:

$$E^*E - (m+Vp(x))^2 = -d/dx d/dx U(x) / U(x) + d/dx U(x) d/dx Vp(x) / (E+m+Vp(x)) U(x) \quad ((9))$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have attempted to show one may obtain the one dimensional bound state Dirac equations with a scalar potential using the idea of spatial flux. In particular, one writes $E^*E - (m+Vp(x))^2$ as two factors $(E + m + Vp(x))$ and $(E-m-Vp(x))$. Each of these represents a different average momentum so one may consider two spatial fluxes $-i d/dx U(x)/U(x)$ and $-i d/dx V(x) /V(x)$, one for each factor. Taking the nonrelativistic limit, however, does not yield the proper $d/dx d/dx W(x) / W(x)2m$ form for kinetic energy. Adding $a(x)$ and $a^{-1}(x)$ to the two average momentum expressions i.e. $(E + m + Vp(x)) a(x)$ and $(E-m-Vp(x)) a^{-1}(x)$ allows one to remedy the situation. One is then able to find a solution for $a(x)$ namely $U(x)/V(x)$ which leads to the bound state Dirac equations in one dimension.

References

1. Narrow Band Schwarzschild Radiation Balance Equations
http://home.pcisys.net/~bestwork.1/QQM/dimension_dirac.htm